

Programmable Quantum Key Distribution Network for Dynamic and Multi-Granular Key Allocation

Florian Honz⁽¹⁾, Vana Pezelj⁽¹⁾, Valeria Saggio⁽¹⁾, Winfried Boxleitner⁽¹⁾, Michael Hentschel⁽¹⁾, Philip Walther⁽²⁾, Hannes Hübel⁽¹⁾, and Bernhard Schrenk⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Center for Digital Safety & Security / Security & Communication Technologies, 1210 Vienna, Austria.

⁽²⁾University of Vienna, Faculty of Physics, Vienna Center for Quantum Science and Technology (VCQ), 1090 Vienna, Austria.

Author e-mail address: florian.honz@ait.ac.at

Abstract: We demonstrate a QKD scheme enhanced with flexible key-rate allocation. A dynamic secure-key rate range of 18.7dB (76×) is obtained through programmable spectrum and detector choice, enabling a fine-grained and efficient use of network resources. © 2026 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The rapid technological advances in the field of quantum computing are anticipated to threaten the long-term secrecy and security of digital information, as currently widely used asymmetric cryptographic algorithms could be broken by large-scale quantum computers. A solution to this problem is provided by quantum key distribution (QKD), a paradigm harnessing the laws of quantum physics to provide information-theoretic secure encryption, and thus mitigating even the security threats posed by quantum computers [1]. Nowadays, QKD has reached a level of technological maturity that enables its integration into commercial systems through deployed fiber networks [2]. QKD has been explored in a variety of communication ecosystems such as optical network units at the access layer [3], yet the complexity of such architectures demands a simplified QKD solution accommodating a variety of services that necessitate a flexible allocation and provisioning of secure-key rates. This arises because the traffic demand in optical networks is inherently not uniform. While some users may need only a small amount of secure-key, some others may require a much higher key rate to securely transfer information across larger infrastructures such as datacenters. Thus, the QKD system must be able to (i) support all key requirements simultaneously, providing the requested amount of keys to all users in parallel, and (ii) provide a dynamic re-allocation of key capacity, in case users suddenly necessitate less or more keys.

In this work, we demonstrate programmable key allocation through wavelength-selective switching (WSS), which dynamically assigns spectral slices and detector classes to each network user over a range of 18.7 dB, depending on their secure-key demand. Our key rate allocation approach serves as an enabler for efficient utilization of network resources. Additionally, it propels the development of high-density QKD networks with simple silicon encoders, where fast adaptability to evolving traffic demands and service differentiation among users are necessary.

2. Fine-Grained Resource Allocation for Key-Rate Elastic QKD Network

Figure 1a presents the concept of a programmable QKD network for the specific case of a point-to-multipoint (p2mp) architecture, as found in x-haul networks or fixed-access networks including professional and corporate users with dedicated fiber lines. Network users at reach L_n from the central office (CO) are equipped with the quantum transmitter (QTX), which in this specific work operates a polarization-encoded BB84 protocol. Motivated by the cloud paradigm, the quantum receivers (QRX), as the more complex element of the unidirectional QKD link, remain centralized. The identical QTXs emit over a common and broad spectral range, with an aggregated launch power μ_{TX} that adheres to requirements of weak coherent pulse systems, i.e. $\mu_{TX} \leq 0.1$ photons/pulse. In order to separate the users while introducing dynamic key allocation at the same time, spectral slices are defined for each of the users by a flexible branching node. For this, a network controller translates the secure-key requests of the network users into a corresponding slice width, which is proportional to the per-user raw-key rates. Since the launch μ_{TX} is unaffected by this mechanism, the resulting μ_n after slicing is defined by the spectral occupancy of the users, meaning that $\mu_n < \mu_{TX}$. By equipping the QRX with two different types of detectors, in particular InGaAs single-photon avalanche detectors (SPAD, $\eta = 10\%$, $T_{dead} = 25 \mu s$, DCR ~ 450 Hz) and NbTiN superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPD, $\eta = 90.5\%$, $T_{dead} = 35$ ns, DCR ~ 15 Hz), a high secure-key rate (SKR) can be acquired even for impairment-restricted spectral

slice widths by dedicating a high-efficiency SNSPD to the corresponding user. Since the broadband emission in combination with polarization encoding can lead to depolarization effects when transmitting over a longer fiber reach [4], reach-dependent transmission impairments are additionally considered when allocating the spectral slice width. To offset the loss in provisioned key rate, the choice of the single-photon detector class is added as an extra granularity for dynamic key adjustment. It shall be stressed that the branching node can be in principle implemented in a virtually passive manner [5], so that no electrical supply needs to be installed at the outside fiber plant.

The corresponding experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1b. A single user is equipped with a QTX based on a monolithic integrated silicon quantum-photonics encoder reported in [6], which generates and manipulates light to produce the four BB84 polarization states within the same chip. The QTX produces quantum signals with a symbol rate of 100 MHz, and performs pulse carving to 50% of the symbol period. Its broadband light emission [6] is then truncated to a CWDM window $\delta\lambda$ (see inset in Fig. 1b), yielding $\mu_{TX} = 0.1$ photons/pulse. The signal propagates over an optical link to the 9×1 WSS, where the dynamic spectral allocation according to a slice $\delta\lambda$ is performed, to then reach the QRX at the CO equipped with single-photon detectors for quantum state measurement. We then perform frame synchronization, temporal filtering to 5 ns, basis sifting, error evaluation and a SKR estimation.

3. QKD Performance under Variable Spectral Provisioning and Single-Photon Detector Allocation

Figure 2a presents the SKR after allocating a specific spectral slice for *Alice* i , considering a variable link reach L_2 after the WSS, to investigate the interplay between spectral slice bandwidth $\delta\lambda$, transmission distance and quantum channel performance. As expected, a higher SKR occurs for higher bandwidths and lower distances. However, an optimal behavior at increasing fiber reach is observed at $\delta\lambda = 4$ nm. This result is also visible in Fig. 2b. While distances of up to ~ 8 km allow the SKR to increase with $\delta\lambda$ up to 8 nm (χ), the 4 nm setting yields the highest SKR beyond this range. We attribute this behavior to depolarization effects attributed to a wide signal bandwidth, increasing the quantum bit error rate (QBER) and therefore lowering the SKR. As shown in Fig. 2c, at a given QBER value the raw-key rate (RKR) increases with the bandwidth $\delta\lambda$, while the fiber reach L_2 , at which this QBER is reached, decreases significantly for $\delta\lambda > 4$ nm. We performed additional studies to further investigate the impact of depolarization on the overall system performance. Figure 3a shows the transmission distance at which the QBER limit of 11% [7], and thus the SKR cut-off, is reached versus $\delta\lambda$, confirming the optimal value of $\delta\lambda = 4$ nm for optimizing the reach between *Alice* and *Bob*. To demonstrate dynamic SKR allocation, Figs. 3b and 3c show RKR, QBER and SKR for two scenarios involving different fiber lengths (4.3 and 12.8 km, respectively). As the depolarization-induced QBER penalty is not significant at 4.3 km, an increase in $\delta\lambda$ from 4 to 8 nm leads to a corresponding increase in SKR (Fig. 3b), evidencing dynamic resource partitioning through spectral slice adjustment. A different situation is observed at 12.8 km (Fig. 3c). Here, an increase in $\delta\lambda$ from 1.6 to 8 nm causes the RKR to increase (an effect to be expected as allocating more bandwidth allows higher counts to be detected, see $\blacklozenge, \blacktriangle, \blacksquare$ in Fig. 2c). However, at the same time the SKR decreases for the change from 4 to 8 nm due to depolarization effects affecting the QBER and thus degrading the system performance.

Next, we investigated the partitioning of the transmission fiber either before ($L_1 \geq 0, L_2 = 0$) or after ($L_1 = 0, L_2 \geq 0$) the WSS. Figure 4a shows the behavior of the RKR (\blacktriangle, \bullet), SKR (\triangle, \circ) and QBER ($\blacklozenge, \blacksquare$) for a variable fiber length segment placed before (dashed) or after (solid lines) the WSS and a slice of $\delta\lambda = 4$ nm. The slightly increased QBER for the fiber after the WSS is due to a $\sim 15\%$ lower RKR and a slight polarization misalignment in the circular basis for distances larger 20 km for L_2 . To provide additional flexibility to the network user's key requests, we performed the same measurements replacing the SPADs with high-efficiency SNSPDs (Fig. 4b). As expected, a lower QBER down to the intrinsic QBER floor of 1.5% for the PIC transmitter and a much higher SKR of up to 51.1 kb/s in a back-to-back scenario is obtained by virtue of the higher detection efficiency and lower DCR. This allows us to address the demand for high-SKR pipes. Figure 4c investigates the ultimate fiber reach L_2 that can be obtained through the use of SNSPDs by comparing the two slice widths of 1.6 (\circ) and 4 nm (\triangle). Here, the narrower slice accomplishes a SKR of 501 b/s for a transmission distance of 55.2 km, enabling us to accommodate even remote network users.

Lastly, we present a passive optical network (PON) like scenario where a user (*Alice* j in Fig. 1b) is connected through a power splitter emulated by a variable optical attenuator (VOA). SNSPDs have been used at *Bob*'s receiver. As Fig. 5 shows, an optical split budget (OB) of 23.1 dB can be accommodated for $\delta\lambda = 8$ nm (\blacksquare) at the SKR cut-off (SKR > 0), which together with the insertion losses for the WSS (4.4

dB) and transmission fibers (3.4 dB) yields an optical end-to-end budget of 30.9 dB between *Alice j* and *Bob*. This means that it is compatible to an XGS-PON class-N1 budget.

4. Conclusion

We have demonstrated a QKD scheme where dynamic key allocation is performed according to the user's demand. We have proven dynamic spectrum allocation in combination with a monolithic integrated silicon quantum encoder and capitalized on additional flexibility by granting access to two different classes of detectors for signal reception. With this, we can facilitate a dynamic SKR adjustment by a factor of 8.3 (due to $\delta\lambda$) \times 9.1 (due to detector), or 18.7 dB at 12.8 km reach. Moreover, we have confirmed the compatibility of the silicon QKD transmitter with class-N1 XGS-PON budgets. The silicon QTX allows scaling to include multiple users in high-density QKD applications.

5. References

- [1] H.K. Lo et al., "Secure quantum key distribution," Nat. Photon. **8**, 595 (2014)
- [2] M. Brauer et al., "Linking QKD Testbeds across Europe," Entropy **26**, 123 (2024)
- [3] S. Bae et al., "Optical Link Design for Quantum Key Distribution-Integrated Optical Access Networks," Photonics **12**, 418 (2025)
- [4] W.K. Burns et al., "Depolarization in a single mode optical fiber," JLT **1**, 44 (1983)
- [5] B. Schrenk et al., "Passive ROADM Flexibility in Optical Access with Spectral and Spatial Reconfigurability," JSAC **33**, 2837 (2015)
- [6] F. Honz et al., "World's First Monolithic SiGe QKD Transmitter Chip," Proc. Opt. Fib. Comm. Conf. (OFC), Th4D.7 (2025)
- [7] P.W. Shor et al., "Simple proof of security of the BB84 quantum key distribution protocol," Phys. Rev. Lett. **85**, 441 (2000)

Acknowledgement: The work was supported by the European Innovation Council under the Horizon Europe program under GA No 101187539, and through the QuantERA II Programme (GA No 101017733) and the Austrian FFG (GA No FO999906040).

Fig. 1. (a) Concept of a programmable p2mp QKD network enhanced with dynamic key allocation capabilities, and (b) experimental setup.

Fig. 2. (a) SKR vs bandwidth and fiber length. (b) SKR vs distance at different bandwidths and (c) QBER vs RKR at varying bandwidths.

Fig. 3. (a) Distance at the SKR cut-off (QBER of 11%). Dynamic optical bandwidth switching for (b) 4.3 km and (c) 12.8 km link reach.

Fig. 4. QKD performance ($\delta\lambda = 4$ nm) with fiber before/after the WSS for using (a) SPADs and (b) SNSPDs. (c) Reach when utilizing SNSPDs.

Fig. 5. SKR vs OB for PON-like distribution networks.